

Recent Investigations on the Heterometallic Alkoxide Chemistry of Cobalt, Nickel and Copper†

R. C. MEHROTRA* and A. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

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A brief review is presented of the methods of preparation, properties and structural characteristics of bi- and tri-metallic heterometal alkoxides of cobalt, nickel and copper. Most of these novel products are volatile and soluble in organic solvents and hence, their applications for synthesis of ceramic materials by MOCVD as well as by sol-gel process are highly attractive.

Metal alkoxides, $M(OR)_n$, are a highly reactive class of compounds¹⁻³ and in view of their solubility, volatility and ease of purification, they are proving to be versatile precursors for preparation of ceramics both by sol-gel⁴⁻⁷ as well as MOCVD^{8,9} (metal organic chemical vapour deposition) techniques. From the homogeneity of the final ceramic product obtained from a mixture of metal alkoxide precursors, Dislich¹⁰ conjectured about the role of new chemical bond formation in addition to the more intimate physical mixing in the solution.

A large number of bi- and poly-heterometal alkoxides have been synthesised in our laboratories during the last two decades⁷. It has been shown that the basic framework of heterometal alkoxides remains unaltered^{11,12} during hydrolytic reactions and hence, the advantages of using presynthesised heterometal alkoxides as precursors are obvious¹³, over the use of mixtures of component alkoxides in which cases, homogeneity is brought about mainly by their random combinations.

One of the characteristic features of the homo- and heterometal alkoxides is the tendency of the metals ($M = M'$ or $M = M''$) to attain coordinative saturation via alkoxo-bridging of the type $M(\mu-OR)_2M'$ between similar and dissimilar metal atoms. The later 3d (Co, Ni, Cu) metals are bivalent in their common oxidation state, resulting in highly polymerised non-volatile insoluble characteristics,

due to which these could receive only scanty attention^{3,7,14}.

Although the formation of heterobimetallic alkoxides in the form of alkoxo-salts was first detected in 1929 by Meerwein and Bersin¹⁵, the isolation of stable and volatile derivatives like $NaZr_2(OR)_9$ by Bartley and Wardlaw¹⁶ gave an entirely new orientation to the field. The formation of such species was not only confirmed in our laboratories¹⁷, but their covalent characteristics (e.g. volatility and solubility in organic solvents in spite of the strongly electropositive nature of alkali metals) were demonstrated in the conductometric titration of a solution of $Zr(OPr^i)_4$ (in isopropanol) with alkali (Na or K) metal isopropoxide.

The first review in 1971 by Mehrotra and Mehrotra¹⁸ dealt with those products which were termed as 'double alkoxides' (at that time). With the discovery of alkoxides containing more than two different metal nuclei, these were renamed as polymetallic alkoxides¹³. However as this term could be confused with polymeric alkoxides of one metal only, these have now been named by the authors as 'heterometal alkoxides', a name which has been readily adopted, e.g. in two recent reviews by other active researchers.

During the last 25 years, synthesis of a large variety of stable heterobimetallic alkoxides¹⁹⁻⁷⁴ involving alkoxometallate ligands of the types : $Al(OR)_4^-$,

†This article is being dedicated to Professor Hiralal Nigam, particularly as he evinced great personal enthusiasm for our entry to the field of later transition metal derivatives, which could be expected to exhibit interesting and revealing spectroscopic and magnetic properties.

* Present address : University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002.

Ga(OR)₄⁻, Nb(OR)₆⁻, Ta(OR)₆⁻, Zr₂(OR)₉⁻, Hf₂(OR)₉⁻ and Sn₂(OR)₉⁻ as multidentate chelating ligands has been achieved.

The first successful isolation of a heterotrimetallic alkoxide was possible in 1985 with smaller beryllium atom⁶⁹. This novel synthesis led the flurry of activities leading to the formation of other fascinating types of heterotrimetallic and polymetallic alkoxides^{49,54,60-62,73}. The recent developments of heterometal alkoxide chemistry of metals and metalloids have been covered in a number of recent review articles^{12,14,74}.

As this article is mainly concerned with the heterometallic alkoxides of divalent Co, Ni and Cu, an attempt is being made in the following pages to summarise the existing knowledge about these derivatives under the following headings : synthesis, physical properties, and chemical properties.

Heterobimetallic alkoxides

Synthesis and properties :

Metathetical or self-elimination method has generally been found to be most convenient and versatile. Another procedure, the reactions of two different metal derivatives has also proved to be of great synthetic utility. The first procedure was for the first time exploited in 1979 by Mehrotra and coworkers^{3,36-39,42-65} to isolate hydrocarbon soluble, volatile and monomeric derivatives [M{Al(OPrⁱ)₄}₂] of bivalent later 3d-transition metals (Mn, Fe, Co, Ni and Cu), simple alkoxy derivatives of which are insoluble, non-volatile and presumably polymeric. In the following pages the synthetic utility of the above two procedures are being illustrated by equations and the known heterobimetallic alkoxides are classified as indicated below :

Tetraalkoxoaluminate derivatives^{3,24,50,52,58,66-68}:

(M = Co, Cu)

For the synthesis of the corresponding nickel(II) derivatives, addition of a few drops of pyridine to the reaction mixture was found to facilitate¹⁸ the

reaction, presumably due to the formation of NiCl₂·2C₅H₅N, a comparatively soluble species in the reaction medium used :

Recently, by adopting these reaction types sterically crowded heterobimetallic alkoxides⁵⁸ of the type [M{Al(OBu^t)₄}₂] (M = Co, Ni, Cu) have been prepared as sublimable, coloured solids, soluble in organic solvents and monomeric :

(M = Co, Cu)

Recently, success has been achieved in the stabilisation and isolation of novel tetraalkoxoaluminate derivatives^{52,54} of the type CIM{Al(OPrⁱ)₄} :

(M = Co, R = Et, Prⁱ, Bu^t; M = Cu, R = Et, Prⁱ, Bu^t)

(R = Prⁱ, Bu^t)

Addition of 2-3 drops of pyridine in the last reaction facilitates the reaction possibly either by increasing the solubility of the nickel(II) chloride alcoholate or by forming comparatively soluble adduct of nickel(II) chloride with pyridine, NiCl₂·2C₅H₅N.

The above features have generated unprecedented interest for studying similar reactions with other alkoxometallate ligands such as M₂(OPrⁱ)₉⁻ (M = Zr^{IV}, Hf^{IV}, Sn^{IV} and M'(OPrⁱ)₆⁻ (M' = Nb^V, Ta^V).

Nonaisopropoxodimetalate derivatives^{44,45,50,75,76} :

*Tetraalkoxoantimonate derivatives*⁷⁹ : Interestingly, the reaction of $NiCl_2$ with $NaSb(OEt)_4$ and $NaOEt$ in a toluene/ethanol solution yields an unexpected product $Ni_5Sb_3O_2(OEt)_{15}(HOEt)_4$ ^{79a}, the structure of which has been solved by single-crystal X-ray diffraction technique. By contrast, the reaction of $NiBr_2$ with $2KOEt$ and $Sb(OEt)_3$ in a toluene/ethanol solution follows a different course of reactions yielding green microcrystalline solid $Ni_6Sb_4O_4(OEt)_{16}(HOEt)_4$ ^{79b}.

*Reactions of two homonuclear metal derivatives*⁸⁰⁻⁸⁴ : Interaction of two different homonuclear metal alkoxide complexes in appropriate stoichiometric ratio affords different varieties of heterobimetallic alkoxides according to the reactions :

(thd = 2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-3,5-heptanedionato)

Heterobimetallic alkoxides^{3,67,68} are highly moisture-sensitive, coloured solids or viscous liquids. Most of these are soluble (except methoxide derivatives containing Al, Zr) in organic solvents. The derivatives of the types $M\{Al(OR)_4\}_2$, ($R = Pr^I$, Bu^I), $M\{Zr_2(OPr^I)_9\}_2$, $M\{M'(OPr^I)_6\}_2$ ($M' = Nb$ or Ta) are monomeric, whereas the corresponding chloro-derivatives are dimeric^{67,68} in benzene. The bis-derivatives are all volatile except the niobates and tantallates. However, amongst the chloro-complexes only $ClM\{Zr_2(OPr^I)_9\}$ are volatile.

Chemical reactivity :

Metal-oxygen bonds in metal alkoxides are polarised in the direction $M^{\delta+} - O^{\delta-} - C$ due to high (3.5) electronegativity of oxygen; naturally such polarisation in an alkoxide would be influenced by the electronegativity of both alkoxide and the metal atom (M). The covalent character of M-O bond increases with greater (+I) effect of the alkyl group. The above type of polarisation makes metal-alkoxo species susceptible to attack by both nucleophiles and electrophiles. Reactions^{3,44-45,76,85} with alcohols and β -diketones, etc. are illustrated in Scheme 1.

* Followed by azeotropic removed of liberated isopropanol

Scheme 1 Some typical reactions of heterobimetallic alkoxides of the types (a) $\text{M}\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}')_9\}_2$ and (b) $\text{M}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}')_4\}_2$.

The above alcoholysis reactions have shown interesting variation in the reactivity of alcohols in the order : $\text{MeOH} \gg \text{EtOH}$, Pr^nOH , Bu^nOH , $\text{Bu}^t\text{OH} \gg \text{Bu}^s\text{OH} \gg \text{Bu}^t\text{OH}$, Am^tOH .

The isolation of heteroleptic alkoxometallates like $\text{ClM}\{\text{Al}(\text{OR})_4\}$, $\text{ClM}\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}')_9\}$ and $\text{ClM}\{\text{Nb}(\text{OPr}')_6\}$ has recently initiated considerable interest in the chloride replacement reactions. These studies have resulted in the synthesis of a wide range of new and interesting heterobimetallic alkoxide derivatives and excitingly novel heterotrimetallic alkoxides (described later). Some typical reactions illustrating synthesis of new classes of heterometallic alkoxide systems are presented below .

Heterotrimetallic alkoxides^{49,54,62}

Synthesis and properties :

A number of novel heterotrimetallic isopropoxides of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} have been synthesised by the interaction of chloro precursors (synthesised as

described earlier, as CIM{Al(OPr^t)₄}, CIM{Zr₂(OPr^t)₉}, CIM{Al(OBu^t)₄}, CIM{Nb(OPr^t)₆}) with an appropriate potassium alkoxometallate such as KAl(OR)₄ (R = Et, Pr^t, Bu^t), KGa(OPr^t)₄, KZr₂(OPr^t)₉, KM(OPr^t)₆ (M = Nb, Ta) according to the following reactions :

All these novel trimetallic alkoxides are highly moisture-sensitive, coloured solids or viscous materials, soluble in common organic solvents (e.g. benzene, n-hexane, toluene, dichloromethane, etc.) and are monomeric (ebullioscopically) in benzene. All these heterotrimetallic alkoxides (except those containing [Nb(OPr^t)₆⁻] or [Ta(OPr^t)₆⁻] can be volatilised under reduced pressure.

Spectroscopic, magnetic, and X-ray diffraction studies

A number of physical techniques have been used to investigate heterometallic alkoxides. Infrared spectroscopy has been quite useful for characterising the alkoxide groups^{36-73,75-77} and their different environments, i.e. terminal and bridging sites. The electronic spectral data in conjunction with magnetic data have been of considerable value in indicating the probable geometries of alkoxy derivatives.

X-Ray diffraction investigations of heterometallic alkoxides have been often fraught with problems that arise due to their higher solubility, deformable nature of crystals, disorder and twinning problems. So far the structures of the following complexes have been determined by single-crystal X-ray crystallography : [Co(OCBu^t)₃]₂LiCl(THF)₂, Ba{Cu[OCMe(CF₃)₂]₃}⁸⁰, Na₂Cu [OCH(CF₃)₂]₄⁷⁸, ZrCo₄(μ₆-O)(μ₂-OC₃H₇)₈ (OC₃H₇)₂(acac)₄⁸⁴, BaCu(C₂H₆O₂)_n(C₂H₄O₂)₂ (n = 3, 6)⁸², BaCu₄(OC(R)C(H)C(R)O)₄(OR')₂(HOR')₄ (R = C(CH₃)₃, R' = CH₂CH₂OCH₃)⁸³, Ni₅Sb₃O₂(OEt)₁₅(HOEt)₄^{79a} and Ni₆Sb₄O₄(OEt)₁₆(HOEt)₄^{79b}

Conclusion : Structural feature of each individual species have been discussed in the original papers. These individualistic features demonstrate a remarkable capacity of the central metal atom to arrange the different ligands around it in a manner as to result in the final unique structural environment, and much more detailed work on related species is essential before any cogent correlation(s) can be arrived at.

Novel features and future directions

The stability of these heterometal alkoxides, formed by alkoxy-bridges between dissimilar metal atoms, is obvious from (i) their non-dissociation in

solution to give the insoluble polymeric alkoxides of bivalent metals and (ii) their volatility (in unchanged form) under reduced pressure. These, therefore, appear to add a new dimension to the existing knowledge of heterometal coordination species, which generally require the presence of metal-metal bonds or/and auxiliary ligands (e.g. Co, C₅H₅, etc.) for their stabilisation. More quantitative data as well as theoretical studies on the structural features of this novel class of compounds are, therefore, called for.

The formation of two types of derivatives with the same basic composition, e.g. tetrahedral⁵⁸ (Bu^tO)₂Al(μ-OBu^t)₂Ni(μ-Obu^t)₂Al(OBu^t)₂ and octahedral³⁸ (MeO)₂(μ-OMe)₂Ni(μ-OMe)₂Al(OMe)₂ derivatives opens up the possibilities of synthesising two types of nickel spinels NiAl₂O₄ with the same composition, but 4 and 6 oxygen atoms around nickel.

The synthesis of soluble alkoxides of metals like bivalent copper again points to the use of such planned presynthesised derivatives for synthesis of novel ceramic materials^{7,8} including superconductors. Their volatile nature opens up a new direction for potential applications of these fascinating class of compounds, in MOCVD process⁸ for the preparation of useful thin films.

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References

1. D. C. BRADLEY, D. P. GAUR and R. C. MEHROTRA, "Metal Alkoxides", Academic, London, 1978.
2. D. C. BRADLEY, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1972, **15**, 259.
3. R. C. MEHROTRA, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1983, **26**, 269.
4. L. G. HUBERT-PFALZGRAF, *New J. Chem.*, 1987, **11**, 663.
5. R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 1988, **100**, 1.
6. R. C. MEHROTRA, in "Sol-Gel Science and Technology", eds. M. A. AEGERTER, M. JAFELICCI, JR., D. F. SOUZA and E. D. ZANOTTO, World Scientific, 1989, 1-60, 421-431.
7. R. C. MEHROTRA, *Chemtracts*, 1990, **2**, 389
8. D. C. BRADLEY, *Chem Rev.*, 1989, **89**, 1317.
9. D. C. BRADLEY, *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. London, Ser. A*, 1990, **330**, 167.
10. H. DISLICH, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1971, **10**, 363.
11. K. JONES, T. J. DAVIES, H. G. EMBLEM and P. PARKES, *Mat. Res. Soc. Symp. Proc.*, 1986, **73**, 111.
12. R. C. MEHROTRA, A. SINGH and U. M. TRIPATHI, *Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **19**, 1287.
13. R. C. MEHROTRA, *Mat. Res. Soc. Symp. Proc.*, 1988, **121**, 81.
14. K. G. CAULTON and L. G. HUBERT-PFALZGRAF, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 969.
15. H. MEERWEIN and T. BERSIN, *Ann.*, 1929, **475**, 113.
16. W. G. BARTLEY and W. WARDLAW, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1958, 421.
17. R. C. MEHROTRA and M. M. AGRAWAL, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 1026.
18. R. C. MEHROTRA and A. MEHROTRA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta Rev.*, 1971, **5**, 127.
19. R. C. MEHROTRA and M. M. AGRAWAL, *Chem. Commun*, 1968, 469.
20. P. N. KAPOOR and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **14**, 1.
21. R. C. MEHROTRA, *Proc. Indian Nat. Sci. Acad.*, 1976, **42**, 1.
22. R. C. MEHROTRA, A. K. RAI and N. C. JAIN, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1978, **87**, 61
23. R. C. MEHROTRA, P. N. KAPOOR and J. M. BATWARA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **31**, 67.
24. R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **52**, 715.
25. S. GOVIL, P. N. KAPOOR and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **15**, 43.
26. R. C. MEHROTRA and J. V. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 109.
27. S. GOEL, A. B. GOEL and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1976, **6**, 251.
28. S. GOVIL and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 138.
29. L. G. HUBERT-PFALZGRAF and J. G. RIESS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 2854.
30. R. C. MEHROTRA, A. K. RAI and N. C. JAIN, 1976, **84**, 98
31. S. GOEL, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Rajasthan, 1975.
32. R. C. MEHROTRA, S. GOEL, A. B. GOEL, R. B. KING and K. C. NAINAN, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, **29**, 131.
33. S. GOVIL and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, **28**, 2125.

34. J. V. SINGH, N. C. JAIN and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1979, **9**, 79.
35. E. STUMPP and HILLEBRAND, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1979, **34**, 262.
36. R. C. MEHROTRA and J. V. SINGH, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1984, **522**, 211.
37. R. C. MEHROTRA and J. V. SINGH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 1046.
38. R. C. MEHROTRA and J. V. SINGH, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1984, **62**, 1003.
39. R. K. DUBEY, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1985, **10**, 473.
40. M. C. AGARWAL, C. K. SHARMA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1984, **13**, 571.
41. M. C. AGARWAL and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1984, **14**, 139.
42. J. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1984, **13**, 273.
43. J. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1984, **9**, 148.
44. R. K. DUBEY, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1986, **118**, 151.
45. R. K. DUBEY, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Polyhedron*, 1987, **6**, 427.
46. A. SHAH, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 485.
47. R. K. DUBEY, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1988, **61**, 983.
48. A. SHAH, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **141**, 289.
49. R. K. DUBEY, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1988, **341**, 569.
50. R. K. DUBEY, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **143**, 169.
51. A. SHAH, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 392.
52. R. C. CHHIPA, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 396.
53. G. GARG, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 881.
54. R. C. CHHIPA, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1990, **20**, 289.
55. S. SOGANI, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 1990, **13**, 375.
56. R. GUPTA, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 596.
57. A. SHAH, R. GUPTA, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1991, **21**, 609.
58. G. GARG, R. K. DUBEY, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Polyhedron*, 1991, **10**, 1733.
59. U. M. TRIPATHI, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Polyhedron*, 1991, **10**, 949.
60. R. GUPTA, A. SINGH, and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 592.
61. R. GUPTA, A. SHAH, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *New J. Chem.*, 1991, **15**, 665.
62. G. GARG, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 688, 866.
63. A. SHAH, J. SINGH, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 1020.
64. R. K. DUBEY, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 156.
65. A. SHAH, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 886.
66. R. C. MEHROTRA and A. K. RAI, *Polyhedron* (Report, No. 28), 1991, **10A**, 1967.
67. R. K. DUBEY, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Rajasthan, 1986.
68. G. GARG, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Rajasthan, 1991.
69. U. M. TRIPATHI, A. SINGH, R. C. MEHROTRA, S. C. GOEL, M. Y. CHIANG and W. E. BUHRO, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 152.
70. S. SOGANI, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 1992, **15**, 197.
71. S. MATHUR, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Polyhedron*, 1993, **12**, 1073.
72. M. C. AGARWAL and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Polyhedron*, 1985, **4**, 845.
73. R. K. DUBEY, A. SHAH, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas.*, 1988, **107**, 237.
74. W. G. VANDER SLYUS and A. P. SATTELBERGER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 1027.
75. R. JAIN, A. K. RAI and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Inorg. Chem. (China)*, 1987, **3**, 96.
76. A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, Unpublished results.
77. R. JAIN, A. K. RAI and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1985, **40**, 1371.

78. A. P. PURDY, C. F. GEORGE and J. H. CALLAHAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 2812.
79. U. BEMM, R. NORRESTAM, M. NYGREN and G. WESTIN, (a) *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 2050; (b) 1993, **31**, 1597.
80. A. P. PURDY and C. F. GEORGE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 1969.
81. N. N. SAUER, E. GARCHIA, K. V. SALAZAR, R. R. RYAN and J. A. MARTIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 1542.
82. C. P. LOVE, C. C. TORARDI and C. J. PAGE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 1784.
83. W. BIDELE, V. SHKLOVER and H. BERKE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 5561.
84. R. SCHMID, A. MOSSET and G. GALY, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1991, **179**, 167.
85. J. SINGH, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Delhi, 1980.